

Real Time Image Stabilization Of An Unmanned Aerial Vehicle In One Dimension

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ABSTRACT

UAVs that are equipped with cameras to capture video or still images suffer from shaky and blurry effect due to inherent vibration of the vehicle resulting from the motion of rotor and wind resistance which causes the captured images/video to be shaky, blurry and less useful for intelligent purposes. Several methods have been used to damp these vibrations mostly through the use of gimbal which is a mechanical device or through the use of either real time image stabilization software which consume a lot of power and introduce latency in the images obtained. The other option is to process the original unstable images, which is not convenient for real time application. In this work a real time image stabilization system has been developed using low power dc motor to counteract the vibration of the onboard camera with single PID controller. The overall system was modeled and simulated in MATLAB/SIMULINK environment. From the simulated results it was observed that the camera was better stabilized with the PIDF than the PID. Also, when the robustness of the system was tested by varying the amplifying factor from 50% to 250%, PIDF coped better, with responses' settling time being less than 20 millisecond (ms) and percentage overshoot (POV) less than 2% compared to that of PID whose settling time is more than 20ms and its POV greater than 2%. This clearly shows the superiority of the PIDF over the conventional PID. The developed system stabilizes the camera better at a lower cost with lower computational overhead than the software image processing methods or the gimbal system.

Keywords: image stabilization system, captured images/video

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) or drone is the name given to vehicles that fly with no human controller on board (Eisenbasis, 2004). Interest in the development of UAVs was strongly motivated by military applications in the 1970s when some nations began looking for cheap and effective means for surveillance, reconnaissance and penetration of hostile terrain without endangering the lives of their pilots or other expensive machines (Elkholy, 2014). At the same time Engineers in the United States also started experimenting with smaller, slower and cheaper UAVs that mimicked large airplanes. Considerable progress has been achieved over the years as these vehicles became larger and more capable, leading to successful deployments in several missions in the mid-1990s. Due to their reconnaissance and tactical capabilities, UAVs are now a major component of modern warfare, especially in the fight against terrorism (Eisenbasis, 2004)

Although UAVs were initially deployed for military missions, due to their extreme flexible nature they are increasingly being adopted for civil applications including firefighting, pipeline surveillance, law enforcement, assessment of natural disasters and environmental monitoring (Elkholy, 2014). It is usual for

UAV to carry payloads that make them useful in any application area. These payloads are usually separated from the drone itself and include high and low resolution cameras for still image or video capture, day and night reconnaissance equipment, military gadgets and so on. (Gupta *et al*, 2013).

1.1 Camera Payloads

In surveillance applications, UAV usually carry cameras to capture scenes in real time however such captured images suffer from jitters due to inherent vibration of the vehicle and wind resistance. As a result, images obtained may not be useful and reliable to guarantee the success of the mission, thus the need to isolate the camera from such vibrations so that more stable images may be obtained. Plate I shows a drone delivering goods.

Plate I: UAV Delivering Goods
Source: Connolly K.B., (2016)

1.2 Statement of the Problem

One of the most important applications of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) is in the field of real time surveillance made possible by a camera payload. However, the images sent by the camera are unstable and jittery because of the inherent vibration of the vehicle. In this work an image stabilization system that serves as a support for mounted camera was developed; the system enables the camera to capture more stable and clearer pictures and can be used for real time purposes.

1.3 Aim

The aim of this research work is to stabilize the position of a camera mounted on a UAV so as to capture stable images useful for real time surveillance application

The objectives are:

- i. To develop the vibration models of some real UAVs from data available in literature
- ii. To design appropriate PID and PID with filter (PIDF) controllers that stabilize the position of a camera mounted on a UAV.
- iii. To compare the performance of the systems when controlled by the designed PID and PIDF controllers
- iv. Simulate the performance of the controllers under different vibration conditions

1.4 Justification of the Study

Image stabilization system was required to eliminate vibrations onboard of the UAV for a vision-based surveillance application. For this purpose, a low-cost, light-weight and reliable stabilization system with an efficient PID Controllers is needed.

1.5 Scope of the Work

This work is designed to stabilize the position of a camera in one dimension only, since this can be replicated for other axes.

2.0 RELEVANT LITERATURE

Many authors have previously worked on the image stabilization for diverse application using different approaches, for example Shih and Stone (2010), described an image stabilization model for vehicle navigation system that can remove the effects of vertical vehicular motion due to road bumps. It uses a wheel sensor that monitors the wheel's reaction with respect to road disturbances. The system employs an

inexpensive sensor and control circuitry which is capable of eliminating 10 cm of drift and results in only 1 cm disturbance at the start and end of bumps. Although results showed a better stabilized image, this approach is mechanical requiring springs and damper as additional hardware.

Also Vazquez & Changs (2009), presented a real-time smoothing methodology for the stabilization of videos captured from small robotic helicopter platforms. Their approach uses Lucas-Kanade feature tracker to detect the regions and then estimate the transformation between two consecutive frames. Unintended motion compensation is accomplished by adjusting for extra rotation and displacements that generate vibrations. The method requires image processing software which is time consuming and costly.

In a similar work, Hu *et al.*, (2007) developed a method that removes the shaky frames from video images, so that the reconstructed output is a stabilized video with better visual quality than the original. In this work, the Scale Invariant Features (SIFT) was used to estimate the camera motion. Results obtained showed that unwanted vibrations were separated from the intentional camera motion by a combination of the Gaussian kernel filtering and parabolic fitting. The method requires series of software image processing approaches and thus time consuming.

Wang *et al.*, (2011) also reported a work on real-time video stabilization for UAV. The stabilizations task was achieved in three steps: Firstly, the key points were located based on Features from Accelerated Segment Test (FAST) corner detection and preliminarily matched. Secondly, the matched key points were estimated to reduce false matching key points. Finally, motion estimation was performed based on affine transform model and the compensation for vibration was conducted based on Spline smoothing. The proposed method was tested for video stabilization in the real video captured by camera installed on UAV, and experimental results showed the efficiency and accuracy of the algorithm but in the case of noise or blur image due to camera quality and transmit distortion, the algorithm for video stabilization is not robust, because it only traces certain points. Secondly it requires much of software image processing methods to achieve stable video.

Plasencia *et al.*, (2012), in a paper titled, Modeling and Analysis of Vibrations in a UAV Helicopter with a Vision System, generated a range of vibrations originating in the main rotor and designed a control system in order to damp these vibrations. The UAV vibration was modeled using VehicleSim software, the vibrations that appear on the fuselage were analysed to study their effects on the on-board vision system by using Simmechanics software, after which a control system based on an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) was implemented to achieve satisfactory damping of the vision system. The results showed that based on the semi-active device with the damping provided by an ANFIS, a clearer image was obtained however this method is quite computational intensive and requires additional software.

In a similar work by Windau & Itti (2011), a real-time video image stabilization system (VISS) was developed for aerial robots. Its architecture combined four independent stabilization layers. Layer 1 detected vibration via an inertial measurement unit (IMU) and performs external counter movements with a motorized gimbal. Layer 2 damps vibrations by using mechanical devices. The internal optical image stabilization of the camera was represented by Layer 3, while Layer 4 filters the remaining vibrations using software. The result showed improved camera footage but it depended on the combination of the interaction of all four layers. This method is applicable to large aircraft thus is expensive for UAVs.

Manohar & Ananda (2015), presented a work titled the Design, Simulation and Development of Two Axes Gimbal for holding and controlling the position of camera in Micro Aerial vehicle (MAV). The gimbal mechanism was used to keep the camera pointed at the target position by compensating the disturbances and vibrations caused by UAV while tracking target. While MAV was navigating, the gimbal rotates with help of servo motors to keep the camera focused on the target. The camera position was adjusted along the roll, pitch and yaw axes by using three servo motors. Positional encoders were used as the feedback element to measure and stabilize the orientation of gimbal. This proposed system cannot guarantee stable quadrotor movement also it is mechanical in nature and additional hardware such as the gimbal is required.

2.1 The Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) Controller

The PID controller consists of three basic feedback control actions, namely proportional, integral and derivative, which represent the current, past and anticipated future errors that cover all the time history of the error signal. The relevant gains are K_P , K_I , and K_D (Sangyam et al, 2010). By adjusting these parameters, the performance and stability of the system can be achieved. PID controller can be implemented in parallel form, series form and standard form. (Win et al, 2018). The structure of the PID is shown in Figure 1 and can be represented as shown below:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(t) d\tau + K_d \frac{d}{dt} e(t) \quad \dots(1)$$

Where K_p is Proportional gain, K_i is Integrator gain and K_d is Derivative gain

Figure 1: PID Controller Structure
Source: (Sangyam et al., 2010)

The controller is to generate an appropriate signal that cause the plant to compensate for the error in $e(t)$, such that

$$e(t) = r(t) - y(t) \quad \dots(2)$$

Where $e(t)$ is the error, $r(t)$ is the reference position and $y(t)$ is the actual position

This signal generated by the controller will cause the motor to move in a direction as to cause the error to be zero, that is

$$e(t) \rightarrow 0 \Big|_{t \rightarrow \infty} \quad \dots(3)$$

The control signal $u(t)$ is given in equation 1.

The performance of a controlled system is measured by its rise time, settling time, maximum overshoot, steady state error etc. These parameters are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: System Measurement Parameter
Source: (Jinghua, 2006)

2. Proportional-Integral-Derivative-Filter (PIDF) Controller

The PIDF means Proportional-Integral-Derivative-Filter. This is shown in Figure 3

The PIDF controller is a PID controller with a filter on the derivative term (Astrom, 2002)

PIDF is presented as shown in equation:

$$K(s) = K_p + K_i * \frac{1}{s} + K_d * \frac{s}{T_d s + 1} \quad \dots (4)$$

Figure 3: Structure of PID with Low Pass Filter
Source: Astrom (2002)

The filter time constant was selected to reduce the process variable noise corresponding to fast disturbances. The PID controller only cannot remove fast disturbances because they are too slow.

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter presents the design procedure for the control system, including the modeling of the UAV vibration model, the modeling of the brushless dc motor used as actuator for the camera mount and the design of the PID and the PIDF controllers. In addition, the simulation procedure was described along with the simulation conditions.

3.1 The Structure of the Controlled System

The structure of the controlled system that was implemented is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Structure of the Controlled System

The purposes and functions of the different blocks and signals in Figure 4 are described as follows:

- i. Reference Position $r(t)$: This is the position the camera is expected to maintain. This is achieved when the actuating signal causes the motor shaft to move in a direction as to cause the error in equation (2), to tends to zero as time approaches to infinity.
- ii. Error signal $e(t)$: Is the difference between the position the camera is expected to maintain and the actual position of the camera as a result of the vibration movement of the UAV; The error signal is defined in equation (2)
- i. Actuating signal $u(t)$: This is the signal generated by the PID or the PIDF controller that causes the camera to move so as to compensate for the vibration of the UAV
This actuating signal causes the motor to move in a direction as to cause the error to be zero, as time approaches infinity as shown in equation (3)
- ii. Noise $N(t)$: Noise signal is used to account for model and parameter mismatch in the controlled system that is vibration model, UAV and measurement errors.
- iii. Actual Position $y(t)$: This is the actual position of the camera
- iv. The UAV Vibration Model: The vibration models were obtained from literature;

The first was adopted from the work of Plasencia *et al.*, (2012) who modeled a UAV Helicopter with the use of VehicleSim (a software specialized in analyzing vibration of different UAVs) and generated a range of vibrations originating in the main rotor and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was used to analyse and generate the frequency spectrum of vibration.

The second case was obtained from Salvador *et al.*, (2014) who also obtained the vibration model of the Sikorsky UAV using VehicleSim, the vibrations were generated by inducing a mass imbalance on the rotors of the vehicle, by doing this, vibrations appears on the main rotor and tail rotor. These vibrations were transferred to the fuselage and analysed using a FFT, from which the vibration amplitudes at different frequencies were obtained, so that the actual vibration patterns were reconstructed and used as the vibration parameters.

The third case was from the work of Du *et al.*, (2014) who modeled a UAV named DX Star UAV using identification method and generated a range of vibrations from the main and tail rotors. Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) was used to analyze the vibrations appearing on the fuselage. From the FFT of DX Star UAV, the vibration amplitudes at different frequencies were obtained.

The vibration amplitudes at different frequencies were obtained randomly for the fourth and fifth vibration model for UAVs and named as Generated Vibration (GV1) UAV and Generated Vibration 2 (GV2) UAV and used as vibration parameters.

- v. Actuator: The Actuator is BLDC servo motor on which the camera was mounted. It was used for the camera positioning

3.2 Modeling of the BLDC Motor

The actuator used in this work was a BLDC servo motor on which the camera was mounted. It serves to position the camera at the reference position as the UAV vibrates; hence the motor moves the camera contrary to the UAV vibration so that the overall movement of the camera is zero with respect to the reference position $r(t)$. BLDC motors are known to have precise angular positioning with a quick response when embedded into feedback control system (Ogata, 2010). The model of the servo motor is developed from electromechanical representation of Figure 5.

Figure 5: Electrical Equivalent of DC Servomotor

For this work the DC motor parameters were adapted from Rick (2013). From Figure 5 above

V_a , I_a and R_a are the armature voltage, current and resistance respectively.

The armature voltage equation is given by:

$$V_a(t) = R_a I_a(t) + L_a \frac{dI_a(t)}{dt} + E_b(t) \quad \dots(5)$$

where E_b is the back emf, while motor torque T_m and armature current I_a are related by a constant K_T such that

$$T_m(t) = K_T I_a(t) \quad \dots(6)$$

The back emf $E_b(t)$ is related to the angular velocity by

$$E_b(t) = K_T \omega_m(t) \quad \dots(7)$$

also

$$K_T \omega_m(t) = K_T \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

$$J_a \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + B_a \frac{d\theta}{dt} = K_T I_a(t)$$

Where J_m (Nm^{-1}) is the moment of inertia of the load on the shaft and θ is the angular displacement ... (8)
hence

$$L_a \frac{dI_a(t)}{dt} + R_a I_a(t) = V_a(t) - K_T \frac{d\theta}{dt} \quad \dots(9)$$

Applying Laplace transform to equations (8) and (9) we obtain

$$J_a s^2 \theta(s) + B_a s \theta(s) = K_T I_a(s) \quad \dots(10)$$

$$L_a s I_a(s) + R_a I_a(s) = V_a(s) - K_T s \theta(s) \quad \dots(11)$$

If current is obtained from equation (11) and substituted into equation (10), we have

$$J_a s^2 \theta(s) + B_a s \theta(s) = K_T \frac{V_a(s) - K_T s \theta(s)}{R_a + L_a s} \quad \dots(12)$$

The transfer function from input voltage, $V_a(s)$ to angular velocity, $\omega_m(s)$ is given as in equation (13).

$$\frac{s\theta(s)}{V_a(s)} = \frac{K_T}{[(R_a + L_a s)(J_m s + B_m) + K_T K_B]} \quad \dots(13)$$

The relation between angular displacement and velocity is

$$\omega(t) = \dot{\theta}(t) \quad \dots(14)$$

$$\omega(s) = s\theta(s) \quad \dots(15)$$

The transfer function from the input voltage $V_a(s)$ to the output angle θ is

$$G_a(s) = \frac{\theta(s)}{V_a(s)} \quad \dots(16)$$

$$\frac{\theta(s)}{V_a(s)} = \frac{K_T}{s[(R_a + L_a s)(J_m s + B_m) + K_T K_B]} \quad \dots(17)$$

Figure 6 is the block diagram representation of BLDC showing elements of the transfer function while the parameters of the DC Motor used are presented in Table 1.

Figure 6: Block Diagram of Separately Excited DC Servo Motor

Table 1: Parameters of DC motors

J_m	Moment of inertia of the rotor	3.2284×10^{-6} (Nms ² /rad)
K_T	Motor torque constant	0.0274Nm/A
R_a	Armature resistance	4.0Ω
L	Electric inductance	2.75×10^{-6} H
K_B	Motor speed constant	3.5077×10^{-6} V/rad

Source: Rick (2013)

While the values of the PID/PIDF gains and performance parameters obtained from the tuning are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Controlled Parameters and Performance

Parameters	PID	PIDF
K_p	5.8959	5.7611
K_i	17.9395	8.9704
K_d	0.084839	0.054575
T_f	-	48.022×10^{-6}
Performances/Indices		
Rise time t_r	0.0108 sec	0.0109sec
Settling time t_s	0.0422 sec	0.017 sec
Percentage overshoot (POV)	2.28	1.54

3.3 Fast Fourier Transform

Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is a fast algorithm for the computing of the discrete Fourier transform (DFT), of a sampled (digital) signal. The components are amplitude of the harmonics present in the original digital signal (Bracewell, 1989). The Fourier equation is the sum of a series of sinusoids of different frequencies and their amplitudes waveform such that

$$V(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{10} a_n \sin \omega_n t \quad \dots(18)$$

where a_n is the amplitude of the waveform at frequency ω_n

Therefore a fast Fourier transforms converts a signal in time domain into its frequency components or harmonics and thereby provides frequency information about the signal. FFTs are used for fault analysis, quality control, and condition monitoring of machines or systems (Gavin, 2018).

3.4 Mathematical Analysis of Vibrations

Several authors such as Placencia *et al*, (2012), Du *et al*, (2014) and Salvador *et al*, (2014), have used specialized software such as Vehiclesim to analyze the vibration of different UAVs and the vibration data were converted into their harmonics using FFT.

Thus using equation (18), equation of vibration can be written as ...(19)

$$v(t) = a_1 \sin \omega_1 t + a_2 \sin \omega_2 t + \dots \dots a_n \sin \omega_n t$$

Ten (10) dominant frequencies were used in order to obtain a better reconstruction. Using small number of frequencies will not give a good reconstruction because the more the frequencies added the better the reconstruction.

The vibration analysis carried by Placencia *et al.*, (2012), Du *et al.*, (2014) and Salvador *et al.*, (2014), were adopted and used as standard vibration parameters. Two others readings were incorporated randomly and used as vibration parameters for the UAV

3.5 The Controller

In this work a PID and a PIDF controller were implemented. Their function is to generate the control signal $u(t)$ that causes the BLDC motor to rotate so as stabilize the position of a camera mounted on it in order to stabilize the reference position despite the vibrations of the vehicle hence it helps to obtain a stable image. The values of the PID/PIDF gains and performance parameters obtained from the tuning are shown in Table 2 while the structure of the PID controlled system is given in Figure 7.

3.5.1 The PIDF controller design

The equation for the PIDF Controller is

$$K(s) = K_p + K_i * \frac{1}{s} + K_d * \frac{s}{T_d s + 1} \quad \dots(21)$$

The design task was to determine K_p , K_i and K_d and T_d , using the same criteria set for the PID Controller.

Figure 7: Structure of the Controlled System for PID Controller

3.6 Simulation Conditions

Firstly, the system was modeled and simulated without controller in a MatlabSimulink environment as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Structure of the uncontrolled System

Secondly, the systems were modeled and simulated with controllers in a MatlabSimulink environment. Figure 9 and 10 show the controlled system with all system equations for PID and PIDF controllers.

Figure 9: Structure of the Controlled System for PID

Figure 10: Structure of the Controlled System for PIDF Controller

Thirdly using the BLDC motor parameters values presented in Table 1 and the controlled parameters of Table 2, the system was simulated under actual vibration (100%) condition using the reconstructed FFT values of frequency and amplitude adopted from Placencia et al, (2012), Salvador (2014) and Du et al, (2014), presented in Tables 3 to 7, in the UAV vibration model.

After which the system was simulated under 50%, 75%, 150%, 200% and 250% reduction and increment in the magnitude of multiplying factor. Figures 11 to 45 give the graphs when system was simulated under various vibration conditions with different multiplying factors.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the results of simulations in graphical form. The PID parameters such as K_p , K_i , K_d and the performance of camera position on a vibrating platform using PID and PIDF (PID with filter time constant, T_f) was evaluated on the basis of settling time, rise time, maximum overshoot etc. Various scenarios were considered and the results compared by the use of the PID and PIDF.

The models were developed in SIMULINK and the results plotted in MATLAB m-file. The simulated system is shown in Figures 9 to 11. Two scenarios were considered. Firstly, the camera position was considered without controller effects. Secondly, five (5) scenarios were generated from the vibration model from the parameters of Tables 3 to 7. Each vibration scenario was varied by multiplying it with different multiplier factor in order to obtain a different variant used in testing the robustness of the system.

4.1 Simulation Results

Simulations were carried out and results shown. Figure 11 showed the results of simulating the model without a controller for unmanned helicopter. While Figure 12 gave the result with and without controllers when magnitude of vibration was multiplied by a factor of 1

Figure 11 showed the response without a controller for Unmanned Helicopter. It was observed that the

Figures 11: Camera Position obtained without Controller for Unmanned Helicopter

Figure 12: Camera Position for Unmanned Helicopter with 100% Vibration

position of the camera is exactly the same as the vibration of the UAV. While Figure 12 gave the result obtained using PID, PIDF controllers and without controller when the vibration was multiplied by a factor of 1, that is by 100% vibration, which represent the actual vibration. Results showed that PIDF reduced vibration amplitude by 86% while PID reduced vibration by 77%. Thus, PIDF coped more efficiently than PID.

4.1.1 Camera position with controllers: decreasing vibration

Figure 13 showed the response when the magnitude of vibration was multiplied by 0.75, while Figure 14 showed the result when the system was multiplied by a factor of 0.5

Figure 13: Camera Position for unmanned Helicopter with 75% Vibration

Figure 14: Camera Position for Unmanned Helicopter with 50% Vibration

The positions of the camera using PID, PIDF controllers and without controller are shown in Figures 13 and 14. From Figure 13, it was observed that PIDF reduced the vibration magnitude by 78%, while PID reduced vibration by 70% using a multiplying factor of 0.75. Figure 14 showed that when vibration was multiplied by a factor of 0.5, PIDF reduced the vibration magnitude by 72% while PID reduced by 55%. Thus from the response it was observed that the controllers were able to cope better in Figure 14 when the multiplying factor was reduced by 25% (multiplied by 0.75) than when it was reduced by 50% (multiplied by 0.5) as in Figure 14. In both Figures however, PIDF coped better than the PID.

4.1.2 Camera position with controllers: increasing vibration

The system was simulated for Unmanned Helicopter with PID, PIDF controllers and without controller using a multiplying factor of more than 1 that is 1.5, 2 and 2.5 as shown in Figure 15 to 17. Figure 15 showed the response when the magnitude of vibration was multiplied by 1.5. Figure 16 showed the result when the magnitude of vibration was multiplied by 2 and Figure 17 gave the response when the magnitude of vibration was multiplied by 2.5.

Figure 15: Camera Position for Unmanned Helicopter with 150% Vibration

Figure 16: Camera Position for Unmanned Helicopter with 200%

Figure 17: Camera Position for Unmanned Helicopter with 250% Vibration

Figures 15 to 17 shows the camera position without controller and with PID, PIDF controllers when the magnitude of vibration was increased for Unmanned Helicopter. Figure 15 showed that when the magnitude of vibration was multiplied by 1.5, PIDF reduced the amplitude of vibration by 89% while PID reduced by 85%. A further increase of multiplying factor by 2 showed that PIDF had reduction of 93% while PID reduced by 90% which is shown by Figure 16. Figure 17 showed that when the magnitude of vibration was multiplied by a factor of 2.5, there was a 94% reduction in amplitude of vibration by PIDF while PID reduced by 92%. In all cases result showed that PIDF was able to compensate for the system better as shown from Figure 15 to 17.

5.0 Summary

In this work a PID controller validated by a PIDF was used to demonstrate and compensate for sinusoidal vibrations applicable to UAV systems. The overall system was stimulated using MATLAB/SIMULINK. Also all details of the PID controller were presented, including the analytical aspect. The controllers gave good performance in terms of rise time, Percentage overshoot and settling time. The PIDF controller showed a better response compared to its PID counterpart. The robustness of the PID and PIDF were also tested to ascertain its ability to eliminate external disturbance.

5.1 CONCLUSION

In this work, a PID and PIDF controllers were used to stabilize the input from a vibrating platform. Since the vibration form of small types UAV is close to sinusoidal vibration, a simple harmonic motion was employed as the vibration. Frequencies and amplitudes of vibration were determined from a Fast Fourier transform spectrum of some real UAVs from data available in literature and results stimulated using PID and PIDF to verify responses of controllers to various input values of vibrations, after which same procedures were carried out for nominal vibration values. Comparing the two controllers, from stimulated result the followings were deduced:

1. The PIDF was more efficient in compensating for errors, thus, it is a better stabilizer than the PID
2. The PIDF has better performance because maximum overshoot, rise time and settling time were better than that of the PID
3. The PIDF has more sensitive response against varying vibration disturbance input than the PID
4. With the PIDF a stable and clearer image was obtained, the response followed the step input response efficiency.

5.2 Contribution to Knowledge

At the end of this work, the following contribution were made

1. How to use of electrical actuator with PID controller to stabilize the image from an on-board camera of the UAV without additional software.
2. UAVs can now capture stable and clearer images for intelligent uses
3. This is applicable for real time purposes

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

In this work, the use of PID and PIDF controllers to steady the position of the camera on a UAV in order to obtain clear images in one dimension only was demonstrated with appreciable results. Further work could be extended to two or three dimensions. Also opportunities for future work in this field could also include the following:

1. Application of different optimization methods to the system
2. Introduction of artificial neural network to the system
3. Physical building of a small UAV and carrying out the various tests

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